

Building Facade Optimization Based on Hidden Water of Materials

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Abstract:

Due to the reduction of energy reserves in the world, optimization in the construction industry is more important than ever. One of the effective examples in energy saving is paying attention to sustainable building materials. In this regard, energy and hidden water of building materials can play an important role in energy efficiency. There are several priorities in the selection of materials by architects and experts, but unfortunately, the attitude towards materials in terms of stability and optimality, especially energy and hidden water is not a priority. In this regard, due to the significant amount of hidden water in the materials, in the production process and also at the time of use, research is necessary. From this point of view, the purpose of the research is to formulate criteria and methods for using construction materials with less hidden water in the building, including optional and mandatory criteria. In order to achieve the amount of hidden water of each building material, first the researches were analyzed, then some materials were analyzed in the field and interviews with experts and specialists of manufacturing companies, and finally the classification of common and new materials in terms of hidden water. Presented as a matrix. This analysis shows that refractory bricks and traditional bricks as well as GRC concrete with an average of 1.7 liters per kilogram have the least hidden water in the production process and steel products with an average of 70 liters per kilogram have the most hidden water. Finally, in this study, solutions to reduce water consumption in the construction industry were proposed.

Keywords:

Hidden water, Hidden energy, Optimality, Sustainable materials, Building facade.

1.1. Introduction:

Architects have a decisive role in identifying and using materials because by having knowledge in the field of how to use products and their correct use in the building, they play a role as a representative of new achievements [1]. The correct and accurate selection of materials reduces energy consumption [2] and approaches the goals of sustainability [3-4]. In this regard, one of the important elements in the direction of sustainability that has been neglected is the hidden water of building materials. Identifying materials from the point of view of hidden water and energy consumption in production stages and stages of use gives us a better understanding of their use in construction [5-6].

Hidden water is the amount of water that a commodity or an agricultural product consumes during the production process to reach the stage of evolution [7] and its amount is equal to the sum of the total water consumption in different stages of the production chain from start to finish [8-10]. Meanwhile, due to the water shortage in Iran, attention to water consumption in various fields, including the construction industry will double the importance of the issue. But today it is observed that water consumption in the process of production and construction of materials is ignored. In this regard, one of the important elements of the building in which materials have a special place is the facade of the building [11-16]. Due to the increase in the level of the facade and its role as an interface between outdoor and indoor space, as well as its special importance in relation to energy consumption, attention to it is felt more than ever.

It is very important to use a method that, in addition to reducing energy consumption, does not limit the design of buildings. A successful façade system is a façade that combines beauty and energy efficiency. In this regard, the question arises- what are the solutions to select and use materials with less energy consumption in the façade of buildings? Therefore, in this research, it is tried to first study and analyze the practical and common materials in the building facade in terms of water consumption in the production process, and then to identify and introduce materials that have less hidden water.

2. Literature Review:

in an article entitled "Water consumption in buildings: embedded water in construction materials", which is taken from a doctoral dissertation, Papí explores the traces of hidden water in materials. In this article, the life cycle of materials is mentioned and it is stated that in order to track the hidden water of materials, first the manufacturing technology and manufacturing

process must be considered and identified in order to extract more accurate information. It is also stated that sometimes it is necessary to search for accurate statistics across borders and continents and around the world. The approximate final numbers of this field of research are also mentioned. In this article, the hidden water per square meter of the building is calculated. The materials that are most used in construction are presented in a table of hidden water dimensions. The conclusion of this article is that for every square meter of the building, there is about 5.6 cubic meters of hidden water [17-20].

In a dissertation entitled "Water Footprint of widely used construction" written by Ruben Bosman, the water footprint in steel, glass, and cement materials is studied and analyzed. Many studies have been done in the agricultural sector to reduce water consumption, but in the industrial sector, the study of water footprint is very small. In this study, production processes are examined and explored. Materials have a great impact on the amount of hidden water, many materials are energy-intensive and can be due to electricity consumption in the production process [21].

Given the very high importance of the issue, especially for countries with water crises, it can be said that the research conducted to date is of particular importance in this area. In order to prove and get closer to the goals, different parts of the construction process in this field should be examined. It is essential to consider hidden water and hidden energy as a part of our integrated thinking about high performance architecture [22-26]. Therefore, due to the high diversity of materials in building facades and the importance of hidden water in it, the present study first tries to identify and introduce common materials in the facade, in terms of hidden water. And then offers solutions for the correct and accurate selection of materials in the facade.

3. Methodology:

In this research, data collection has been done in the form of a library, field studies, observation and interviews with experts. In this study, the basic information of hidden water in different sources was studied. First, each material was analyzed separately. Due to the different methods of material production, in some cases of information in different sources, there was a difference in the number of cases, so in order to obtain accurate and precise information, the need for further investigation and analysis of objective samples was felt. As a result, in order to extract more accurate information, we referred to some factories that produce materials. Interviews with experts and familiarity with the process of producing materials and collecting information

were conducted in the field in the next stage. The list of face-to-face interviews as well as scientific sources and analyzed articles can be seen in the table-1 below.

Table. 1: Sources obtained from interviews and articles

Face-to-face interview with experts of Hegmataneh Cement Factory in Hamedan
Face-to-face interviews with diamond sand factory experts
Face-to-face interview with the experts of the Azimi Qarchak brick factory in Tehran
Face-to-face interview with experts of Sina Refractory Brick Factory in Hamedan
Interview with experts of Heidari Varamin brick factory
Face-to-face interview with experts of Rad Hamadan Steel Factory
Face-to-face interview with experts from Alkawaston factory in Hamedan (production of composite sheets)
In-person interview with Hamedan Aral ceramic tile Production Company
In-person interview with the experts of Ardakan Glass Production Factory
Face-to-face interview with experts of Hamedan Alvan Paint Production Factory
Interview with experts of Alvand facade stone factory in Hamedan
Article: Email interview with Dr. Juan Antonio Ferriz-Papi Professor, University of Salford, England
Article: Virtual water accounting for building: case study for E-town, Beijing
Article: The blue and grey water footprint of construction materials: Steel, cement and glass
Thesis: Assessment of water footprint for civil construction projects
Assessment of water resource consumption in building construction in India
Water consumption in buildings: Embebed water in construction materials
Embodied energy and carbon in construction materials
Life cycle assessment in buildings: State-of-the-art and simplified LCA methodology as a complement for building certification
Thesis: water accounting for a building construction engineering project with nine subprojects: a case in E-town, Beijing
THE STRUCTURE OF THE BUILDING LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT (LCA) FOR SELECTING SUSTAINABLE MATERIALS IN RESIDENTIAL COMPLEXES IN TEHRAN
Water is required for the production of materials and construction of two residential towers in Tehran with skeletons of Steel and concrete

Water consumption in the production of building materials and consumption optimization proposals
Calculation of water footprint in the construction industry, comparison of concrete and steel structures

Source: Authors

All the information obtained from regular books, articles and materials as well as the information obtained from the author's interview with materials production specialists were categorized in an Excel program and analyzed in tables. Due to the fact that the initial information had different units, all units of measurement were standardized in terms of water consumption in liters per kilogram. All materials that were used in different types of building facades were identified and the facade design method was analyzed. For each type of material, the hidden water was calculated based on the square meter in the facade. Facade components were divided into three categories: main facade materials, facade connecting materials and final facade covering. Each of them separately has hidden water in the production process and also water at the time of use was calculated and finally the hidden water of one square meter of the executed facade of the building was extracted. 30 common and common materials were identified in the facades of the building is observed.

Table. 2: The amount of hidden water of materials in the production process (liters/kilogram)

Name of materials	Liters/kilogram	Name of materials	Liters/kilogram
Handmade brick	.7		
Firebrick	.12	Fiber cement board	1.6
Black sheet	76	GRC concrete	.7
Galvanized sheet	136	Exposed concrete	1.1
Colored sheets	100	Aqua Panel	.8
Stretch Metal	86	Thermo wood	1.8
Metal section	76	Plast wood	5
Aluminum sheet	13	Sun Coler	4
Copper sheet	60	Knitex paint	5
Matt steel	76	Mineral	1.9
Porcelain ceramics	14	White cement	1.1

Granite	1.8	Bayramics	1.5
Cement Plast	.95	Marble	1.9
Artificial Stone	.9	HPL	30
Composite sheet	20	Mono Light	1.1
		Glass	.5

Source: Authors

4. Results:

In this section, the weight of each square meter of the desired facade is calculated and based on the amount of hidden water obtained in the previous table, which was extracted in liters per kilogram, is presented in the table below. It should be noted that the amount of hidden water mentioned includes the stage of production of materials, time of use, connecting materials and possible final coverage. According to this table, it can be seen how much water has been consumed in each of the common views to be exploited. By comparing them, materials with less hidden water were prioritized in terms of stability. The results reconfirm the literature

Table. 3: The amount of water hidden in the production and operation stage

Name of materials	Hidden water content (liters/kg)	Hidden water in the production process (liters / m ²)	Water at the time of use (liter / m ²)	Concealed water Facade connection materials (liters / m ²)	The amount of water hidden in the final layer (liters / m ²)	Hidden water of the entire production cycle to use in the facade (liter / m ²)
Hand brick 20 * 10 * 5/5	0/7	94/5	10	18	1	122/5
Hand brick 20 * 5/5 * 3	0/7	44/1	17	18	1	79/1
Hand brick 20 * 20 * 3	0/7	47/25	17	18	1	82/25
Refractory brick 32 * 7 * 2/5	0/12	6/048	12	18	1	36/048
Refractory brick 20 * 20 * 2/5	0/12	5/4	12	18	1	35/4
Black sheet 3 miles	76	1786	1	456	1	2243
galvanized sheet 2 mil	86	1376	1	456	1	1833
Colored sheet 1 ml	100	800	1	456	0	1257
Corten sheet .5 mil	30	1200	1	456	0	1657
video punch sheet 2 mile	86	1376	1	456	0	1833
Stretch metal 2 miles	86	1376	1	456	0	1833

Box profile 10 @ 20 * 20	76	1178	1	76	1	1255
Box profile 10 @ 30 * 20	76	1444	1	76	1	1521
Box profile 10 @ 40 * 20	76	2280	1	76	1	2357
Aluminum sheet 1 mil	13	35/1	1	247	0	283/1
Copper sheet 1 mil	60	162	1	600	0	763
Patinated copper 1 ml	80	216	1	800	0	1017
Matt steel .7 mil	76	836	1	760	0	1597
China dry porcelain ceramics	14	156	1	304	0	461
Slurry porcelain ceramics	14	280	22	546	0	848
Granite	1/8	100/8	22	70/2	0	193
Travertine	1/7	85	22	66/3	0	173/3
Marble	1/9	102/6	22	74/1	0	198/7
Tablet stone	1/9	114	22	74/1	0	210/1
Plast cement run with adhesive	0/95	39/9	0	0/95	0	40/85
Plast cement run with slurry	0/95	39/9	22	37/05	0	98/95
Artificial stone granite and marble-adhesive	1	44	0	1	0	45
Fireproof cement fiber	16	160	0	304		464
GRC concrete	0/7	13/3	1	76	0	90/3
Exposed concrete	1/1	44	1	152	0	197
Wet hair	1/8	12/96	0	760	0	772/96
Plast wood	5	85	0	1444	0	1529
Color Sun Carler	4	1/2	0	72	0	73/2
HPL	30	300	0	150	0	450
Mono Light	1/1	27/5	6	0	0	33/5
Composite sheet	20	400	1	760	0	1161
Single-walled glass with metal frame	0/5	7/5	0	9/5	0/25	17
2-glazed PVC frame	0/5	15	0	9/5	0	24/5
Double-walled thermal break glass	0/5	15	0	9/5	0	24/5

Source: Authors

5. Model simulation:

To better understand the analysis and numbers obtained in the previous tables, 10 different facade samples were simulated on the same volume with different materials and the hidden water of each facade was calculated separately. The windows are also in the same volume and are a fixed number. The results can be seen in the following tables.

Table. 4: Analysis of simulated sample of brick and granite façade.

	Total hidden water	Hidden water (windows)	Hidden water materials 2	Hidden water materials 1	Meters	Materials 2	Meters	Materials 1
	22650	1225	14475	6952	75	Black granite	88	Brick 20 * 3 * 5

Source: Authors

Table. 5: Analysis of simulated sample of Firebrick

	Total hidden water(Liter)	Hidden water- windows (Liter)	Hidden water materials 1(Liter)	Meters	Materials 1
	6930	1225	5705	163	Firebrick

Source: Authors

Table. 6: Analysis of simulated sample of Porcelain ceramics

	Total hidden water(Liter)	Hidden water- windows (Liter)	Hidden water materials 1(Liter)	Meters	Materials 1
	76368	1225	75143	163	Porcelain ceramics

Source: Authors

Table. 7: Analysis of simulated sample of Sheet Metal

	Total hidden water(Liter)	Hidden water- windows (Liter)	Hidden water materials 1(Liter)	Meters	Materials 1
	702125	1225	700900	163	Sheet Metal

Source: Authors

Table. 8: Analysis of simulated sample of Exposed concrete

	Total hidden water(Liter)	Hidden water- windows (Liter)	Hidden water materials 1(Liter)	Meters	Materials 1
	33336	1225	32111	163	Exposed concrete

Source: Authors

Table. 9: Analysis of simulated sample of Patinated copper

	Total hidden water	Hidden water (windows)	Hidden water materials 2	Hidden water materials 1	Meters	Materials 2	Meters	Materials 1
	147946	1225	89496	57225	75	Patinated copper	88	copper

Source: Authors

Table. 10: Analysis of simulated sample of Thermo wood

	Total hidden water(Liter)	Hidden water- windows (Liter)	Hidden water materials 1(Liter)	Meters	Materials 1
	238553	1225	237328	163	Thermo wood

Source: Authors

Table. 11: Analysis of simulated sample of Composite sheet

	Total hidden water(Liter)	Hidden water- windows (Liter)	Hidden water materials 1(Liter)	Meters	Materials 1
	190468	1225	189243	163	Composite sheet

Source: Authors

Table. 12: Analysis of simulated sample of GRC concrete.

	Total hidden water(Liter)	Hidden water- windows (Liter)	Hidden water materials 1(Liter)	Meters	Materials 1
	15895	1225	14870	163	GRC concrete

Source: Authors

Table. 13: Analysis of simulated sample of Granite

	Total hidden water(Liter)	Hidden water- windows (Liter)	Hidden water materials 1 (Liter)	Meters	Materials 1
	32684	1225	31459	163	Granite

Source: Authors

6. Conclusion:

A smart choice for building facades in materials that have less hidden water and at the same time have beauty and efficiency will save millions of liters of water per year. This article tried to make common materials in facades that have less hidden water. Provide analysis and identification for a better understanding of a simulated model. Finally, the factors that can reduce water consumption in the life cycle of a building can be summarized as follows:

1- **Durability:** The higher the durability and life of materials, consequently less water is consumed in the life cycle of materials, in other words, the need for production is reduced and as a result less hidden water is consumed.

2- **Facade connection components:** The smaller the number and complexity of the connectors of the main materials to the building, the lower the water consumption will be. In some cases, the latent water of the connectors is greater than the latent water of the main materials.

3- **Integrated material selection:** When choosing materials, paying attention to stability, hidden energy and hidden water of materials can be effective in reducing energies, especially water.

4- **Weight:** The lower the weight of the materials used in the facade, the less need for raw materials and consequently less hidden water will be

5- **Reuse strategies:** The use of second-hand and recycled materials is a strong step in order to save water consumption from the hidden water dimension.

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